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INTEGRATION MAPPING OF REFUGEE
AND MIGRANT CHILDREN

IMMERSE D5.2-M6_V1.3

IMMERSE DELIVERABLE D5.2

Stakeholder Engagement Activities and Training Programme

VERSION 1.3

Contract No: 822536

Summary

The aim of the Stakeholder Engagement Activities and Training Programme is twofold. While the programme is intended to propound basic facilitation skills and tools for the researchers, it has been agreed upon that it will also provide a toolbox. Therefore, the first part will lay common ground rules for facilitating the qualitative workshops and focus groups and second part will provide a toolbox, from which all partners can choose appropriate methods which reflect the respective country-specific conditions.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822536

Deliverable Nr. 2	Work Package Nr. 5	Task/s Nr. 5.2
Work Package Title	Social Awareness and Stakeholder Engagement	
Linked Task/s Title	Co-creation Engagement and Activities Programme	
Status	Final	(Draft/Draft Final/Final)
Dissemination level	PU	(PU-Public, PP, RE-Restricted, CO-Confidential)
Due date deliverable	M6	Submission date M8
Deliverable version	V1.3	

Approval status

FUNCTION	NAME	DATE	SIGNATURE
Deliverable responsible	DOZ e.V.	30.07.2019	
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Document History

1 Version	2 Date	Comment
V.1.1	25.02.2019	
V.1.2	19.07.2019	
V.1.3	30.07.2019	

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Training Programme

IMMERSE aims to enhance the socio-educative inclusion of all refugee and migrant children through the generation of a dashboard of socio-educational indicators that will allow collecting information to be analysed and become practical policy recommendations. IMMERSE aims to implement co-creation methods to involve children and other relevant stakeholders in the generation of the dashboard, the data collection and the generation of policy recommendations. In pursuance of these objectives, this manual aims to provide a diverse range of researchers from different countries with the fundamental know-how and skills for an effective facilitation of differently composed groups.

This training programme has therefore been prepared to serve as a guide, reference material, and a toolbox for researchers participating in the qualitative workshops of work package 1 and the data collection of work package 3.

1.2 Objectives of the Training Programme

Since this manual is tailored to the professional technical training of researchers its objectives are as follows:

- Mediation of basic common methodology
- Obtaining basic skills to prepare and facilitate sessions
- Provision of strategies for management of challenges and overcoming obstacles
- Provision of a toolbox of methods

1.3 Format of the Training

Due to geographical differences, the training will be held in the form of a webinar. A webinar is an online seminar or presentation using software tools of video conferencing. Participants typically register using their email address and join in via a personalized link sent by the host. Inside the webinar, participants can see and hear the presenter and each other, view slides and other media like videos, ask questions, and sometimes answer polls. Webinars can be live or pre-recorded. Within IMMERSE, Zabala will host the webinar as a 1 ½ hour seminar in April via an online conference host service.

2 Operating Principles and Workshop Facilitation Principles

2.1 Internal Project Operating Principles for Stakeholder Engagement

To ensure a common standard in facilitating the workshops, focus groups, and other activities the following agreed-upon principles should inform all facilitators, researchers, and project planners in both the planning and the execution stages of all stakeholder activities:

Common Knowledge Base

Benefits from the collective expertise all stakeholders involved, having migrant children's voice at the centre of every activity.

Collaborative Work Environment

Dynamic feedback, validation and promotion of the project's results by stakeholders, taking into account all perspectives, experiences and expertise of participating community members to ameliorate reform proposals, strategies and processes.

Gender and Inclusivity Perspective

Equality will be promoted and considered in each activity.

Proactivity and Engagement

Online and on-site surveys, consultations and workshops will foster first-hand interaction with stakeholders.

Open Dialogue and Communication

Active engagement will improve public understanding of the situation of refugee and migrant children in Europe, raising awareness of the need to measure and monitor refugee and migrant children integration in schools and other learning experiential environments.

2.2 Workshop Facilitation Principles

In taking on the role of the workshop facilitator always be aware of and act upon the following principles:

Neutrality

Our motivation for complying with the principle of neutrality is to ensure that everyone is confident, by abstaining from any participation in hostilities and at all times in controversies of a political, racial, religious or ideological nature. Neutrality includes many dimensions. Only the day-to-day acts can constitute evidence of its respect of the principle of neutrality and thus gain the trust of all and create an environment where every participant feels welcome.

Engagement

Our aim is to encourage and enable everyone affected to be involved, as engagement provides an actual chance to influence a community. The engagement process will be clearly communicated in a way that's easy to understand within a reasonable timescale and using the most suitable method/s for the involved participants to develop their skills, knowledge and confidence at the same time.

Encouragement

For us encouragement is the fundamental attitude of positive feedback that focuses primarily on effort or improvement rather than outcomes. Encouragement is recognizing, accepting, and conveying faith in a participant so that the person feels worthwhile and appreciated regardless of the results he or she achieves.

Communication

To communicate more effectively we want to create a safe environment and actively build trust to achieve productive and effective conversations. Therefore it is indispensable to lead with presence and listen with curiosity and care to understand and finally build a connection and a relationship.

Consideration

While working with participants it is important to carefully think of the needs of everyone and take everyone into regard, as for example in making a decision. Therefore the participants need to be given value and importance.

Respect

Respect is a ground rule for every participant. It starts with listening to each speaking person and his or her ideas and feelings. It also implies the acceptance of everyone's differences and at the same time maintaining one's self-respect.

Patience

When it comes to working with others, patience is of particular importance as it helps foster a calm and productive environment. Patience enables you to maintain a calm demeanour and results in better decision making and understanding the feelings of others. Overall this will lead to reduced stress levels among participants.

Structure

Structure is very important as it gives your workshop direction and makes it easier to attain the final goal. Without structure it is easy to become side-tracked and go off topic. Having a well-structured workshop will also help with time management and give participants a framework so that they are aware what progress they have made.

3 Training Content

3.1 Core Facilitation Tools

This chapter is to provide basic knowledge about the facilitation of participatory settings and the engagement of different stakeholders.

3.1.1 Participation and Engagement Formats

One of the objectives of IMMERSE is to achieve meaningful participation in order to obtain an extensive and precise picture about the situation of refugee and migrant children in six countries. Since the project is involving a variety of different stakeholders, engagement and participation have to be adapted respectively.

Participatory assessments need to be age appropriate. This means adapting the methods, content and our expectations according to the age and developmental stage of the child. For instance, a workshop session with six-year olds will not directly produce a large volume of detailed textual information; it will still provide a picture of these children's lives, their concerns and a sense of their well-being. It will give us an opportunity to engage and observe these children to cross-reference their views with that of other age groups.¹

Engaging and facilitating participation is possible in a wide variety of ways. Different formats and respective methods can be used for different occasion, objectives, and target audiences. The following list is meant to provide a short, if not complete overview over main formats.

Interview

A research interview is a conversation between a researcher, who "coordinates the process of the conversation and asks questions"² and an interviewer, who answers researcher's questions. Interviews can be led from the researcher in a face-to-face meeting, over Internet or over the telephone.³ There interview can be structured, semi-structured or unstructured.

Seminar

A seminar is a meeting of a group of people with a teacher or expert for training, discussion, or study on a particular problem or subject. The seminar is a popular form of knowledge transfer. The seminar offers a deeper engagement with a subject than a lecture and is characterized by a small group and an increased interaction of the students.

¹ UNHCR. 2012. 8.

² Easwaramoorthy and Zarinpoush Fataneh. 2006. 2.

³ Easwaramoorthy and Zarinpoush Fataneh. 2006. 2.

Workshop

A workshop is usually a brief, educational program for a relatively small group of people. Workshops do focus techniques and skills in a particular field and is one of the best formats to increase participation and keep it intimate. This format works best for small, more focused audiences and increases flexibility: a part can be online and the other one in real life.

Focus group

The Spiral research centre of the University of Liège defines the focus group as “a qualitative method of social research that fosters the emergence of all opinions”⁴. The method is not concerned with the search for consensus but instead allows for the collection of different perceptions, attitudes, beliefs and areas of resistance within the target groups.

To be precise, the technique targets a different number of participants and aims to stimulate an open discussion among interest representatives responding to the logic of creativity. Working with focus groups is best suited when targeting an analysis and synthesis of a specific subject discussion, which in turn exposes points of convergence and divergence between different stakeholders.

The method makes it possible to gather the perceptions of the stakeholders concerned, without preconceived ideas or verification of a hypothesis. It can explain the attitudes concerning certain issues, causes, and remedies. Focus groups encourage the involvement of the community by giving them the floor. Ultimately, this method provides experts on a decision level the opportunity to develop policies and projects in line with the expectations expressed by the populations or groups concerned.

The success of the focus group is based on four main factors. Recruitment of participants must take place according to homogeneous criteria. It goes without saying that this criterion must be assessed according to the issues studied. The aim here is to form groups where no factor will hinder the communication. The organisation of the group must respect the laws of group dynamics, particularly regarding the direction of the exchanges according to the themes of the grid. The presence of an experienced facilitator is thus indispensable. The development of the grid must meet the objectives of the study and be adapted to the target group. Finally, the synthesis of results should be systematic, with quantified data, i.e. inter-group comparison and percentage.⁵

Congress

A congress refers to a gathering of people working in the same field. This event can last for one day - that's usually referred to as a conference - or as a multi-day event. Congresses serve to exchange information about new insights, further and new developments, and to establish and

⁴ Spirale. 2011-2019.

⁵ Spirale. 2011-2019.

cultivate contacts. The information transfer within the congress takes place via lectures and workshops.⁶

World Café

World café is creative process that aims to facilitate constructive dialogue and the sharing of knowledge and ideas in order to create a network of exchanges and actions. This process reproduces the atmosphere of a café in which participants discuss a question or topic in small groups around tables. At regular intervals, participants change tables. A host stays at the table and summarizes the previous conversation to newcomers. Conversations in progress are then 'fertilized' with ideas from previous conversations with other participants. At the end of the process, the main ideas are summarized in a plenary assembly and the possibilities for follow-up are discussed.⁷

Barcamp

The participants put together the program themselves. It is a conference where participants exchange their knowledge and experience in workshops, lectures and discussions. A barcamp is primarily about the participants learning from each other.

Open Space Technology

Open Space Technology (OST) is a format developed by the European project PRO-Ideal Plus. The biggest advantage of this method is the possibility to perform it with any number of people; i.e. even with a high number of contributors. Participants are asked to define a possible common working agenda and a range of tasks concerning a specific issue to be discussed. OST is best suited for complex issues involving conflict, complexity, and several different people and opinions and short decision-times. Participants presents specific proposals and projects and then move to their preferred topics and groups. Each person who makes the proposal guarantees that they are able to write a report with the outcomes and main issues discussed by the group immediately after the discussion.⁸

3.1.2 Planning the Engagement Activity

3.1.2.1 Settings

When setting up the workshops all facilitators should consider the following:

- Prepare the room carefully and consider a welcoming atmosphere
- Allow for an open order for the settling-in of participants (for example: chair circles)

⁶ Heidenberger

⁷ Slocum. 2006.

⁸ PRO-Ideal Plus. 2010. 9.

- Prepare all the material for the workshop
- Post the ground rules somewhere visible during the workshop.

3.1.2.2 Time Management

“A workshop is both a time consuming and a time saving activity”⁹; time consuming due to the organisational effort involved, time-saving because it provides an environment where all participants can feel addressed differently and appropriately.¹⁰

The following tips can help you to manage the time:

- Choose a time keeper to remind you regularly about the time used and left.
- Create and share a timed agenda. Remind people if/when the group is close to running out of time or over time. Ask the room and get agreement before spending more than allotted time.
- When caught up, cut time from the middle of the activity not from beginning or end.
- Simplify tasks.
- Reduce the amount of discussion time especially those in small groups.
- Reduce reporting time to the larger group.
- Ensure you arrive on time and respect the schedule.

3.1.2.3 Adults – Group Agreement

A group agreement is a set of statements that defines how people will behave within the workshop. It is a very useful tool for starting the workshops in a positive manner and maintaining structure during the session. A group agreement helps the group to work together respectfully and effectively.

A group agreement can be defined by the group or by the facilitator.

Defining a group agreement as a group is far more empowering than having a facilitator set out 'rules' for everyone to follow¹¹. Also, people are much more likely to respect and implement an agreement to which they have had an input. When problems or conflicts arise, you will be able to refer back to this agreement¹². It should however be noted that it takes more time to define the group agreement with the all participants at the beginning of the session than to bring an already written group agreement and ask for their consent. Whether you choose the first or the second method depends how much time you can spend on it. A group agreement can be proposed but not imposed on the participants.

⁹ PRO-Ideal Plus. 6.

¹⁰ PRO-Ideal Plus. 2010. 11.

¹¹ Seeds for Change. Group agreement. 2.

¹² Seeds for Change. Group agreement. 2.

Goals:

- Secure and frames the workshop
- Defines the common rules of the workshop
- Assures that every participant has the same understanding of concepts such as confidentiality and respect

Example of a group agreement:

- Everyone has the right to have their voice heard, but only one at a time (raise your hand and wait for your turn)
- Every participant is aware of the objectives
- Respect different opinions - especially if you don't agree with them – because not everyone has the same experiences and backgrounds
- Confidentiality: what is shared in the group remains in the group
- Respect the activity time. If you need more time, this can be negotiated
- Turn mobile phones off
- If you need a break, raise your hand and ask the group
- Sharing responsibility: everyone contributes to the running of the group
- Listening is important: pay active attention to each member
- If you don't understand something, ask
- Laugh together but not at each other

3.1.2.4 Youth – Group Agreement

Children and adolescents are different to adults in the way that they view, experience and communicate their concerns. They are often excluded from adult decision-making processes and face additional barriers to participation. Participatory assessment is a method developed by the UNHCR and is “an important way of ensuring that boys and girls of all ages and backgrounds are at the centre of decisions concerning their protection and well-being. Effective participation also recognizes children and adolescents as rights-holders, it builds their capacity and resilience, and allows them to better protect themselves and their peers.”¹³

Should you decide to use the group agreement in your workshops accommodate a group-centric decision-making process involving all participants:

- Ask participants to think about the best group discussions they have been a part of, and reflect on what made these discussions so satisfying.
- Next, ask participants to think about the worst group discussions in which they have participated and reflect on what made these discussions so unsatisfactory.

¹³ UNCHR. 2012. 7.

- For each of the positive characteristics identified, ask them to suggest three things the group could do to ensure that these characteristics are present.
- For each of the negative characteristics identified, ask them to suggest three things the group could do to ensure that these characteristics are not present.
- Use participants' suggestions to draft a set of ground rules to which you all agree.¹⁴

Once a group agreement has been reached, make sure it is on display for all to see - ideally have it written up on a whiteboard, flipchart or overhead projector.

3.1.2.5 Children – Ground Rules

Ground rules articulate a set of behaviours expected of the children for workshop conduct. Like for the other type of participants, as facilitator you can define the ground rules together with the group or define them in advance and ask for the agreement and understanding of the children. Once your ground rules have been agreed upon, make sure they are on display for all to see - ideally have it written up on a whiteboard, flipchart or overhead projector.

Approach for working with children:

- Break sessions up into shorter periods so that they are more effective.
- Use drawings, art work and physical props, and talk to the children about what they have produced.
- Use simple 'voting' techniques for young children to express their choices and make decisions – ask them to place items into hoops or use smiley faces to make a decision.
- Use props, stories or puppets to introduce and support the topic.
- Use a range of techniques and activities – a multi-method approach works best.
- Activities should be visual, physical and varied (moving around as one group, working in pairs, dividing into small groups)
- Show the children the results of their participation - for example a drawing or puppet - and let them take it home¹⁵

Active agreement is a useful addition to any group agreement. With the children you can develop a hand signal codex.

3.1.3 Facilitation Welcomes and Farewells

In order to set the mood for the workshop, it is important to open the session in the right way. As such, the facilitator should be assertive in introducing the session and explaining the agenda. This

¹⁴ UNHCR. 2012. 11.

¹⁵ UNHCR. 2012. 11.

ensures that everyone knows who is in charge and who they can turn to in case of questions. Participants should then be given the chance to introduce themselves so that they feel comfortable engaging in activities with the rest of the group. Introductions can be made individually, with each person taking 1 or 2 minutes to say something about themselves to everybody else. Alternatively, split the group into pairs and have each participant introduce themselves to their partner. After 2 minutes, reform the group and ask each member to present the other person.

It is equally important to finish the session in an appropriate manner, so that participants have a sense of closure. Here, the facilitator should recap what has been covered. Focus on positive points and on praising the participants, but also highlight if something needs to be done differently. This can also be achieved using an evaluation form, if appropriate. Use what you have learnt to help form a follow-up plan. You can also ask each participant to present one thing that they have learnt from the session to the group. Round off by employing one of the more energetic exercises from the toolbox, so that everyone leaves with a smile on their face.

3.1.3.1 Icebreakers, Warm-Ups and Energizers

These techniques are used to introduce participants to each other, build rapport, help them wake up, to recapture their wondering interest, or to inject energy into the session. As the name implies, the icebreaker warms the learning environment to the point that the 'ice' keeping participants from interacting with each other melts and activities can begin.

Process

This technique involves a certain level of fun. It is how it is used that makes it an ice breaker. A joke, short game, or physical activity of some sort can all be icebreakers. Integrating personal information such as names, hobbies etc. can help to build bonds faster. For example, to start a class with new participants you might randomly pair off participants. Once in pairs, have participants draw a picture which describes something about them, and then explain it to the group; solve a puzzle together; or take a "blind walk" in which one person (whose eyes are closed) is led by a partner's verbal instructions could be some examples.

What we have in common

Time: 10 minutes

Strengths: This shows which traits the participants share. This information will be useful to draw upon later in the workshop.

The facilitator calls out a certain characteristic which they are sure relates to at least some of the participants. For example, if the facilitator says, 'everyone who has a pet', all of the people who have pets should move to a specified space in the room. As the facilitator calls out more

characteristics – e.g. ‘likes football’ – the participants who this relates to move into a different area.¹⁶

Pictures

Time: 15 minutes

Strengths: This exercise helps participants overcome their fear of drawing and encourages participation in a fun manner.

It is often beneficial to incorporate some sort of creative aspect to the activity, so as to encourage participants to enjoy *and* express themselves. Pictures are particularly useful in this regard, and can be applied in one of two methods:

- a) Bring a picture with you, and have participants discuss what they feel it represents. If necessary, this can be facilitated with guided questions.
- b) Have participants draw their own pictures, which are supposed to symbolise a topic that is thought out and presented by the facilitator beforehand. Convey that the pictures do not have to be artistically sophisticated, but rather seen as shorthand notes. This will encourage the participants to express themselves and boost their creativity.

Whichever method you choose should be followed up with a discussion, whereby the feedback is light-hearted and not focussed on criticism.

Common questions to guide discussion: What can you see in this picture? Is the situation familiar? What are the problems associated with this picture?¹⁷

Name games

Time: 5 – 15 minutes. Participants: 10 to 30.

Strengths: Encourages participants to learn each other’s names in a fun and enjoyable manner.

When you have several people in a group, particularly from different backgrounds, they are likely to have a range of different names. This can be very useful for facilitating introductory activities.

One particular technique for learning each other’s names is as follows:

Everyone selects a verb that starts with the same letter as their name (e.g. Jumping James). Start by throwing a ball to the first participant and perform the action as you say their name. All other participants then copy the action. The ball is then thrown to the next person, performing the action that they have selected (e.g. Laughing Lucy), before proceeding around the rest of the group.¹⁸

Machine

Time: 15 – 20 minutes

¹⁶Larock Otim. 2013. 31.

¹⁷ Larock Otim, 2013. 31.

¹⁸ Seeds for Change. 2009. 16.

Strengths: Good for warming up and gaining trust. It is also appropriate for getting to know each other and raising attentiveness.

Weaknesses: Session is not suitable if the group is already energetic, as it calls for attention and sensitivity.

This exercise encourages participants to pay attention to one another by acting as part of a team. Have everyone line up in against a wall. One participant comes into the room, searches for a position, performs a simple movement, and repeats it, while making a sound that matches the movement. The second person should then perform a follow-up movement and an appropriate sound which intertwines with the first person. Little by little all the other group members join, so that everything results into a complex construct of movements and sounds.¹⁹

Excitement sharing

Time: 30 seconds – 2 minutes per person. Participants: 3 to 20.

Strengths: A fun and personal way to start the workshop

Participants share something exciting with the group that happened to them recently, for example: “my friend came to visit”, “we picked blackberries for the first time this year”, “and I went to a football match”. This creates a lot of positive energy in the room and fosters a bond among participants due to the personal nature of the activity. The news should be kept brief so as to maintain the pace and energy of the exercise. Discourage questions and comments.²⁰

3.2 Facilitation Management and Challenges

As facilitator you are faced with many challenges, such as keeping control of the group or dealing with conflict, disruptive behaviour or difficult questions.

3.2.1 Control

“There is usually a great temptation to take control of a discussion or change a procedure. This often results from a genuine desire to help the group move forwards.”²¹ However, it is not the function of the facilitation management. A facilitator provides a method and a means to deliver answers to complex issues. They need to balance time, the degree of uncertainty of the issues, and the process maturity of the organisation/group - and help the task leader to find the best possible process. They understand the continuum of decision-making and change and identify

¹⁹ Zap A Lot. Improvisationstheater Hamburg. 2003.

²⁰ Seeds for Change. 2009. 16.

²¹ Larock Otim. 2013. 18.

the best tool or technique to use.²² The task for a facilitator is to bring structure to situations such as this. An effective facilitator will use an analytical process to define the facts, filter out and appropriately handle opinions, challenge assumptions, provide summaries and ensure that everybody is appropriately involved.

The function of the facilitator is not to control the group during the workshop, but to lead the discussion and give a frame in order to collect relevant answers or interventions about the discussed topic. The fundamental idea is that effective trouble-shooters or facilitators reach conclusions by following a series of clearly defined steps and principles.²³ It is always possible for the discussion to leave the framework set by the facilitator and go off in all directions.

Strategies:

- Redefine the frame of the topic (clearness and structures are needed).
- If a topic is really not working, break your activity and do the opposite of what you are currently doing. For example: If a session with the whole group is not working, build some small groups. If a theoretical discussion is not working, start a practical exercise. On the contrary, if a practical exercise doesn't work, introduce a theoretical discussion²⁴.

Here are several quick and easy methods to gauge group opinion to drop unpopular ideas:

Show of hands

2 - 5 minutes; any number of people

Obvious but effective. Run through your list or agenda and get a preliminary show of hands on how important each item is to the group. Those options that have less support are good candidates for being quickly scrapped. Remember to check with the people that made a suggestion before scrapping it – it is best to avoid upsetting them for the rest of the meeting. It is also possible that an idea that's not popular at first glance can become the favourite on closer examination.²⁵

Fist To five

5 - 10 minutes; any number of people

A more complex version of the show of hands. Group members stick up:

- Five fingers for strong support and a willingness to lead the proposal forward.

²² Mann. 2013.

²³ Kepner-Tregoe. 2011.

²⁴ Larock Otim. 2013. 18.

²⁵ Seeds for Change. 2009. 28.

- Four fingers for strong support, and a willingness to work on it.
- Three fingers for minimal support, but a willingness to work for it.
- Two fingers for neutrality.
- One finger for no support.
- Fist for no support and active opposition.²⁶

Thumbs spectrum

3 - 5 minutes; any number of people

Another simple visual tool. Ask everyone to stand and imagine a vertical axis with support for an idea at the top and no support at the bottom. Get them to stick out their thumb and raise it along the imaginary axis for support (the higher the thumb the more support) or lower it for opposition (the lower the thumb the more opposition). If all the thumbs are up, you know the group likes the idea. If all of them are on the floor, it is not going to work!²⁷

Stickers and dots

5 - 10 minutes; up to 50 people

You can achieve the same effect by giving everyone a number of stickers or dots (1-6 usually works). Write up a list of the ideas. Ask people to stick their stickers or make their dots by the item(s) that they consider to be most important for the group to deal with. If you give multiple dots or stickers, people have the choice of 'spending' them all on one item that they feel is really important/urgent, or spreading them across a number of options.

Ranking

10 - 20 minutes; 5 - 20 people

This is a great technique for using in small groups. Write each option on a card or post-it note and give each group a full set of cards/notes. Set a time limit and ask the groups to rank the options, or reduce the options to, say, three. Having a facilitator in each small group will help. It's also helpful to set out clear criteria at the start - for example:

"You've got 15 minutes. We're looking for options that need to be done most urgently, are most important, and yet realistic within our budget. Also we've only got a week to make it happen, so please think about what we can realistically achieve in the time available."²⁸

3.2.2 Difficult Questions

During the workshops with the different groups, researchers may be asked to address difficult or inappropriate questions. Facilitators often feel they need to have all the answers and may lack

²⁶ Seeds for Change, 2009. 29.

²⁷ Seeds for Change. 2009. 28.

²⁸ Seed for change. Participation. 32.

confidence in their own ability to deal with particular questions.²⁹ There are strategies to deal with complicated questions.

Some general tips for addressing questions during the presentation include acknowledging all questions, being sure that everyone has heard the question by repeating it, and being honest and answering questions directly.

Suggestions for avoiding difficult questions:

- Prepare by reading through the discussion material and familiarising yourself with the concepts and language. Ensure that participants are clear in the meaning.
- Communicate clear expectations, setting the agenda and goals at the beginning of the session.
- Provide basic guidelines for when and how questions will be addressed throughout the training.
- Anticipate potential questions and think of possible responses. Consider which ideas might need further explanation within the group. Let them to know where they can find more information.

Strategies for answering questions:

- It is impossible to know everything. You can always get back to the group later with more information³⁰ or ask the participant to find you after the workshop.
- Guide participants through the process of answering their own questions instead of automatically providing an answer. Ask questions if necessary.³¹
- If the question is too specific, restate the question more broadly so that it is relevant to everyone.³²
- If the question is not related to the material, remind the audience of the focus of the presentation and direct the participant to a relevant resource to learn more.
- The facilitator can offer to write the question, issue or comment on a flip chart so that it can be addressed later with an open question.³³
- Some questions appear to be never ending, such as when participants (or a single participant) ask a barrage of questions. One way to address this without being confrontational is to answer each question as briefly as possible and move to the

²⁹ Larock Otim. 2013. 18.

³⁰ Larock Otim. 2013. 18.

³¹ Larock Otim. 2013. 18.

³² Zamora Durán and Diamond. 2012. 11.

³³ Rotary International. N.a. 20.

next topic. This approach limits the new information for sparking additional questions. Bridging techniques, words, or phrases can be useful.³⁴

- It is important to separate the attitude and tone of the questioner from the content. Participants who were unsuccessful in past attempts or are struggling with a difficult issue may bring a certain scepticism or frustration to the workshop. If so, try to rephrase the question without the confrontational tone and answer the question as honestly as possible.³⁵

3.2.3 Conflict

Sometimes people will have strong and conflicting ideas on a subject and this may also affect the way the group works together as a whole. This can be healthy. It shows that members are taking ownership and sharing their ideas honestly. However, if this escalates and ceases to be constructive it is important to address the conflict as soon as possible.³⁶ Remain sensitive to possible differences and tensions and encourage people to work through them, keeping their common goals and interests in mind.³⁷

Strategy:

- Acknowledge the conflict.
- Try to establish the cause of the conflict.
- If it is related to the topic in question, help lead the participants to a place of agreement, encouraging mutual respect.
- If it is unrelated to the topic, and only involves several group members, encourage them to solve the disagreement later, outside of the group setting.

3.2.4. Disruptive Behaviour

Disruptive behaviour, such as participants using cell phones, participants coming back late, people reading emails, and having conversations while someone is talking to the group. This distracts the other participants too. Passive aggressive behaviour may also arise.

Often, this is displayed by participants who were forced to attend training: the so-called prisoner, or participants who aggressively share their opinions over the interests of other people in the room.³⁸

³⁴ Zamora Durán and Diamond. 2012. 12.

³⁵ Zamora Durán and Diamond. 2012. 12.

³⁶ Thayer-Hart. 2007.

³⁷ Otim. 2013. 19

³⁸ Halls. 2017.

Strategies against disruptive behaviours:

- Regarding disruptive behaviours: prevention is better than cure. One of the key tactics is to develop a rapport with the group.³⁹
- Combat disruptive talking by increasing proximity to the talkers e.g. by walking towards them. This method shows participants that they are disrupting without verbalising the matter.
- If disruptive behaviour continues, speak with the participant during the next break.⁴⁰

3.2.5 Involving Everyone

One of the most important challenges during the workshops is to get the entire group involved and participating. It can happen that a small group dominates the whole discussion and that the other participants feel they don't belong to the group.

Strategy to include the entire group:

- Change the composition of groups for small group work.
- Assign roles to participants in small groups such as leader, timekeeper, recorder, and spokesperson.
- Encourage different methods of reporting group work.
- Create seating arrangements that encourage group discussions.⁴¹

In order to gain the interest and energy of the participants in the room, it is important to start the meeting off in such a way as to gain their full attention. Facilitators should be aware that participants might arrive with the following barriers to participation:

- Confusion about the topic
- Dislike for the topic or adversity towards the nature of the discussion
- Feelings of insecurity based on ability or others in the room
- Feelings of superiority to others in the room or towards the facilitator
- Afraid to see or hear the reaction of others in the room
- Fear of dealing with others in the room due to poor relationships
- Fear of speaking or sharing of ideas in front of others, particularly if a supervisor is in the room at the same time

³⁹ Halls. 2017.

⁴⁰ Zamora Durán and Diamond. 2012. 13.

⁴¹ Otim, 2013. 20.

- Low level of trust in the group, process or facilitator
- Coming from another meeting and still thinking about that content rather than what you might be sharing or facilitating
- A history of not sharing ideas or listening to new concepts – in other words a past history of negativity to project implementation or discussion of the issues at hand
- The facilitator must manage all of these dynamics during the opening of the meeting as well as throughout the entire discussion.⁴²
- The "Law of Two Feet": If at any point you find you are neither learning nor contributing, use your two feet. Go somewhere that you can learn and contribute. This law is a very strong way to foster empowerment, engagement, responsibility and motivation for all participants.⁴³

3.2.6 Dominant Participants

Sometimes one person might dominate the discussion, confident that they have all the right answers. Hostile, aggressive, dominating persons may bully and overwhelm others by bombarding them, sometimes disrupting proceedings when they do not get their own way. The motivating factors may vary depending on the type of aggressive behaviour. Some hostile individuals are task-oriented and want to get the job done while maintaining control.⁴⁴ A good facilitator needs to make sure that others have the opportunity to speak.

Some strategies are:

- Tell the person that he or she is not following the "ground rules" for the meeting.⁴⁵
- Give them time to vent and calm down. Call a time out if necessary.
- Reinforce alternative behaviour
- Introduce a quota system, in which each person is given three stones or bits of paper, and they have to give one up every time they speak.⁴⁶ The number of times each person can speak will be limited, so that each member is treated equally.⁴⁷
- Place them with other similar types or in the same group as the facilitator.
- Stand up for yourself without being threatening and ask questions to show you can move together.

⁴² University of Virginia.

⁴³ PRO-IDEAL Plus. 2010. 10.

⁴⁴ Hinkey and Engleby. 2003. 10.

⁴⁵ Hinkey and Engleby. 2003. 10.

⁴⁶ Larock Otim. 2013. 20.

⁴⁷ Larock Otim. 2013. 20.

- “Dominant people “use” and “play” this domination as a screen. In fact, the vast majority of dominant individuals suffer from a lack of recognition.”⁴⁸ In order to get their attention, give them responsibility within the group.
- Express your own point of view without attacking them in order to avoid confrontation.

3.2.7 Shy Participants

Sometimes people may be very shy or afraid to express their views in a group. Quiet people are non-participative and passive. They can be shy, depressed, and afraid, tired, or have a negative attitude towards the group, instructor, or the process. There are many reasons why a person is shy or quiet. They may just be a shy person or uncomfortable in the particular group setting. This behaviour may be difficult for a facilitator who is seeking interaction and response. However, the participant may not intend to be difficult. Some learners are very cerebral and deliberate. They need time to absorb and reflect on the content. Their method of actively participating may be by taking copious notes or listening very carefully. This person may be shy and uncomfortable speaking up in large groups.

There may be a political reason: someone with greater authority may be present and the person may not feel comfortable speaking up in front of them. Then again, this may be passive-aggressive behaviour intended to make a statement through lack of participation. If their silence is an obstacle to team cohesion, some tricks can unblock the situation.

Strategy for supporting shy people:

- Refer back to and use their ideas, so they know they are important and of value.
- Encourage them individually and give positive reinforcement for any response.⁴⁹
- Understand the reasons for their silence.
- Put people into smaller groups or first ask people to discuss questions in pairs.
- Give notice of the topic before the discussion, so that they have time to prepare.
- Give them responsibility for note-taking and feedback.
- Place them in a supportive group.
- Give them time.
- It is also possible to use other practical activities such as mind-mapping, ranking, seasonal calendars, timelines to help express their views.

⁴⁸ Pénissard. 2018.

⁴⁹ Hinkley and Engleby. 2003. 13.

- Use role-play to build up confidence and skills.⁵⁰ Always offer observer roles as options for role plays, games, or simulations.⁵¹
- Ask open-ended questions.
- Ask the person easy questions to help increase his/her self-confidence.
- Engage the participant by posing a question that directly relates to her situation or concern.
- Call this individual by name and ask for an opinion.
- Draw this person out. If they have chosen a very overt behaviour to trumpet their choice not to participate: Draw the person outside the room, either during an exercise or break.
- Listen when the participants talk to each other. Some people are too shy to talk directly to the facilitator, but they will do so with their colleagues.⁵²

In private:

- During a break, ask the person whether the training is meeting her needs, or simply engage in small talk. Sometimes, that personal interaction will create enough comfort for the person to begin speaking up in class.
- Name the behaviour and ask if there is anything that you can do differently so that the participant will feel more comfortable speaking up.
- Provide constructive feedback about the impact of the behaviour on the session, the participants, and/or the facilitator.
- Coach the person to select more constructive behaviour.
- Co-opt the person – ask for her assistance.⁵³

3.3 Micro-Level Stakeholders (Children)

Traditionally, workshops would be facilitated either as a means or as practice. They have gained in importance as a research method, particularly in qualitative research. Within the framework of the IMMERSE project the workshops will be utilised to facilitate qualitative research, thereby allowing the researchers to narrow in on the set of indicators related to a specific topic.

The following pages aim to provide the researchers in each country with the same set of tools from which they can then apply to their respective country-specific circumstances, school systems, and differing sets of stakeholders.

⁵⁰ Larock Otim, 2013. 20.

⁵¹ Laurel and Associates. 2010. 7.

⁵² Action for the right children. N.a. 17.

⁵³ Laurel and Associates. 2010. 6.

3.3.1 Session – Children 6-9

Group agreement

Strengths

A great exercise for creating a flat hierarchy among all participants at the very start of the session. No one opinion is more important than any other. It also provides structure for the workshop

Weaknesses

There could be some points that certain participants do not agree upon, and this could present an obstacle that has to be overcome.

Aim

To collaboratively create a safe and respectful space where everyone can work together productively.

Objectives

- Include all participants
- Set an agenda
- Resolve differing opinions
- Create a productive space
- Establish rules
- The ability to compromise

Materials

- Flipchart
- Pen

Procedure

Start the workshop by negotiating the group agreement. The key to this exercise is in the name: it only works if everybody agrees on the proposed points as a group.

The idea is to set the tone for how people will behave.

Possible propositions might include:

“Respect everyone’s opinions”; “allow everyone an equal opportunity to speak” (this could be more specific – “no interrupting” for example); “confidentiality”; “mobile phones switched off, or onto silent mode”.

Challenges may arise if some participants do not agree upon a certain point. This will require everyone to discuss and negotiate a solution together.⁵⁴

⁵⁴ Seeds for Change. Facilitation tools. 2009. 5.

Plus-Minus-Interesting

Strengths

Facilitates the discussion of opposing views in calm manner without generating conflict. Can be used for the whole group, small groups, or individuals.

Weaknesses

It could be that certain participants have nothing to say about a particular topic, or it is distressing for them to talk about.

Aim

To encourage participants to understand and accept views that may be different from their own.

Objectives

- Resolve differences
- Include all participants
- Improve listening skills
- Encourage discussion

Materials

- Whiteboard
- Flipchart
- Pen

Procedure

To begin the exercise, the facilitator should write the topic on the whiteboard/flipchart. Then draw a plus sign, a minus sign and an “I”, which stands for “interesting”.

Start with the plus, and ask the participants to name anything they feel is positive about the chosen topic. Write these comments around the plus sign. When everyone has had their say, move onto the minus sign and list points that the participants find negative.

Around the “I” sign, list everything that the participants find interesting, as well as ideas that could be explored further, etc.

If any participant does not want to talk about a certain topic, that is no problem. There will be chance for them to join in with subsequent rounds. What seems positive to one person could be negative to the next.

After completing the discussion about the first topic, move back to the plus sign and start a second round, possibly featuring a topic that was previously under the ‘interesting’ category. This will allow you to build on previous ideas.⁵⁵

⁵⁵ Seeds for Change. Facilitaion tools. 2009. 14.

Skilled Hands Exercise

Strengths

Helps participants to build confidence and pride by focussing on something they are good at.

Weaknesses

Participants who are shy or more insecure may initially have problems identifying their strengths.

Aim

By the end of the exercise, each participant will have found out several things that they are good at. The results usually exceed expectations!

Objectives

- Build confidence
- Encourage discussion
- Foster memory skills
- Learn about other participants

Materials

- Paper
- Pen/Pencil
- Hands

Procedure

Provide all participants with a sheet of A4 coloured paper and a coloured pen/pencil. Ask everyone to draw round their hand and write one thing that they are good at in each of the fingers.

Some may find this harder than others, but this provides an opportunity for the facilitator or other participants to step in and help.

The skills do not necessarily have to be overly complex, and could be something as simple as tying your shoelaces, or riding a bike. This is likely to vary depending on the age group.

Once everybody has thought of five things, Split the group into pairs. Pairs take turns in discussing things they do well, and how they acquired those skills.⁵⁶

⁵⁶ Seeds for Change. Facilitation tools. 2009. 20.

Role-plays and Simulations

Strengths

This exercise enables participants to see things from another person's perspective. The theatrical aspect injects energy into the session.

Weaknesses

Some participants may not want to perform in front of the group, or feel uncomfortable playing a certain role.

Aim

To have participants understand an 'opposing' point of view.

Objectives

- Build confidence
- React to unexpected circumstances
- Improve listening skills
- Understand opposing views
- Enhance reflective skills

Materials

- Possibly props, depending on the scenario selected.

Procedure

The difference between a role-play and a simulation is that in a role-play, participants play somebody else, while in a simulation, they play themselves.

Select a situation you want to be enacted. Take into account what you want to explore and why. A simple situation is best e.g. a misunderstanding with an employee due to language barrier in a shop/train station etc.

Explain the situation carefully, including the groups represented and the physical layout. If issuing roles, never force someone to play something they are uncomfortable with. Give them a few minutes to get into their role. All non-participants act as observers.

The facilitator stops the simulation or role-play when enough issues have been uncovered, the exercise comes to a natural end or people want to stop. The play should also be stopped if a participant shows great tension or gets too involved. Have a short break, de-role (see below) and then evaluate the exercise.

Evaluation allows the observers to comment on proceedings. Leave space for discussion. What have participants learnt and how will they apply this in real life? Observers should be encouraged to make positive comments on what they have seen. Rather than saying what participants should have done, it is better if they use language like "Another option that you might try is...", "Perhaps this would work...", "I learned ... from your tactic and would like to try..."

After any role-play it's important to **de-role**, to come out of the role and leave any strong emotions behind. Assess the level of de-roleing required, depending on the intensity of the role-play. A simple shake or a few deep breaths may be enough. Other options include taking a break, a physical game, or a visualisation that takes people's attention elsewhere (to a pleasant memory, for example).⁵⁷

⁵⁷ Seeds for Change. Facilitaion tools. 2009. 10.

Somebody could play the member of staff, somebody the person speaking a foreign language, and someone else interpreter.

Animal sounds

Strengths

Active, fun exercise that is perfect for younger children. Encourages everybody to interact, including shy participants. Universal appeal, no language barrier.

Weaknesses

Can be quite chaotic and loud. It may be hard for children to regain concentration afterwards. This makes it more suitable for the end of the session.

Aim

To facilitate communication and establish bonds between all participants in a fun fashion. To overcome language/cultural barriers.

Objectives

- Break the ice
- Include all participants
- Release energy
- Liven the atmosphere
- Overcome language barriers
- Have fun!

Materials

- Blindfolds
- Flashcards with animals

Procedure

At the start of the exercise, participants are issued cards with the name of an animal that is recognisable to everyone (cow/pig/duck etc.) There should be at least three 'animals' of each species.

The participants then need to be blindfolded. This provides the first opportunity for interaction, as the children can be asked to blindfold one another. The facilitator can step in and help if necessary.

The challenge is then for the participants to use their respective animal noises in order to find other animals of the same species, before revealing their identity. While the exercise starts off loud and chaotic, it should end up with a feeling of order and unity.⁵⁸

⁵⁸ Seeds for Change. Facilitaion tools. 2009. 38.

3.3.2 Session – Children 10-12

Group agreement

Strengths

A great exercise for creating a flat hierarchy among all participants at the very start of the session. No one opinion is more important than any other. It also provides structure for the workshop

Weaknesses

There could be some points that certain participants do not agree upon, and this could present an obstacle that has to be overcome.

Aim

To collaboratively create a safe and respectful space where everyone can work together productively.

Objectives

- Include all participants
- Set an agenda
- Resolve differing opinions
- Create a productive space
- Establish rules
- The ability to compromise

Materials

- Flipchart
- Pen

Procedure

Start the workshop by negotiating the group agreement. The key to this exercise is in the name: it only works if everybody agrees on the proposed points as a group.

The idea is to set the tone for how people will behave.

Possible propositions might include:

“respect everyone’s opinions”;
“allow everyone an equal opportunity to speak” (this could be more specific – “no interrupting” for example); “confidentiality”;
“mobile phones switched off, or onto silent mode”.

Challenges may arise if some participants do not agree upon a certain point. This will require everyone to discuss and negotiate a solution together.⁵⁹

⁵⁹ Seeds for Change. Facilitation tools. 2009. 5.

Problem Tree Analysis

Strengths

Suitable for small and large groups and includes all participants. Visual nature of the exercise makes it easy to comprehend complex issues.

Weaknesses

If participants do not have direct experience with the issue at hand, they may struggle to find ideas.

Aim

To establish both the causes and effects of a relevant problem as well as their prior and subsequent manifestations.

Objectives

- Improve brainstorming skills
- Build analytical capabilities
- Solve complex problems

Materials

- Whiteboard
- Flipchart
- Pen

Procedure

If you have a large number of people, divide them into smaller groups.

Decide upon a relevant issue. Draw a large tree with a broad trunk and branches/roots that split as they reach further outwards. Write the core issue on the trunk.

Collect ideas from participants and write or draw the various causes and consequences on the roots and branches respectively. Here, you can use the thicker areas for more general ideas, before becoming more specific as they branch out.

This will provide an overview of both primary and secondary factors.⁶⁰

⁶⁰ Larock Otim. 2013. 43.

Case Studies

Strengths

Useful for covering several different topics in a short space of time. Perfect for larger groups. Requires a number of different skill-sets.

Weaknesses

Participants may struggle in adhering to the time limits.

Aim

Foster understanding of important issues through a record-and-recount approach.

Objectives

- Text comprehension
- Build concise writing skills
- Encourage confidence
- Develop new insights

Materials

- Printed case studies
- Pen
- Paper

Procedure

Divide the participants into smaller groups.

Hand out the different case studies to each group and provide more detail if necessary. Allocate a set amount of time for the groups to read and discuss their case study. Then have them write a summary that they will present to the rest of the group.

Once the reading is finished, open up the topic for feedback from the rest of the participants. This will lead to the formation of new ideas.

Bear in mind that the participants may need some guidance in their reading of the text. Consider preparing questions in advance to help them.⁶¹

⁶¹ Engineers Without Borders. 2010. 5.

Six Thinking Hats

Strengths

The activity encourages participants to develop a broad range of ideas by asking them to take on new perspectives. Good for large groups.

Weaknesses

Participants may initially struggle to come up with ideas that do not reflect their own opinion.

Aim

To consider an issue from all possible angles, ranging from the most negative to the most positive outcomes.

Objectives

- Understand different viewpoints
- Encourage interaction
- Develop role-play skills
- Consider an issue thoroughly

Materials

- 6 different coloured hats/pens

Procedure

Split the participants into groups of six and issue each member with a different coloured hat (if you do not have hats, pens are also fine). Each 'hat' represents

Below is one possible order for a creative problem-solving process. The roles the 'hats' bring give you a chance to thoroughly examine every option and to prioritise or choose the best one(s).

- Green hat: These people think creatively in a non-critical, free-thinking manner.
- Red hat: These provide the emotional input of the discussion, allowing themselves to be intuitive and follow their gut feeling. They are sensitive to the emotional responses of others.
- Black hat: Black hats live under a black cloud! They should think pessimistically. Look for the flaws in the plan, find the obstacles!
- Yellow hat: Yellow hats bask in sunlight – they should think positively looking for the value in every possibility. What benefits does it bring?
- Blue hat: The blue hat is worn by the facilitator(s). They concentrate on process, calling on the other hats to add in their thinking as and when it's appropriate and making sure that each option is scrutinized from all perspectives. They are neutral, helping the group achieve its task without trying to shape the decision⁶²

⁶² Seeds for Change. 2009. 33.

a different way of looking at something. Individuals within the group can wear one of the hats whilst the group discuss an issue.

Head, Heart, Feet

Strengths

Encourages participants to reflect on the workshop in a creative style. A good way to close the session.

Weaknesses

-

Aim

To round off the workshop in such a manner that participants have something to go away with.

Objectives

- Build on reflective skills
- Encourage creativity
- Provide a 'take-away' lesson

Materials

- Printed case studies
- Pen
- Paper

Procedure

Post a flip chart drawing of a person on a wall or in the middle of the floor with head, heart, and feet explicitly shown.

Distribute three sticky notes to each participant.

Ask participants to identify three things (one per sticky note) that they learned in the workshop/session: a new idea, a feeling, and an action idea or skill (something they can use outside the workshop/session). (Invite contributions in words, headline form, or drawings.)

Ask participants to put their sticky notes on the larger flip-chart. ⁶³

⁶³ Engineers Without Borders. 2010. 9.

Role-play

Strengths

Group members get new impressions about other people's thinking and feeling. At the same time, participants self-reflect their own thinking.

Weaknesses

Conversation could at some point focus on the same arguments. Facilitators should supervise and encourage the other group members to rotate.

Aim

Allow people to understand both sides of a conflict. Possibly develop a definition of acceptable behaviour (e.g. conflicts over power, sexism, ageism etc.).

Objectives

- Provide participants with an understanding of conflicting parties
- Help people entrenched in one position to think more flexibly
- Useful for examining a critical incident that occurs repeatedly or is expected to occur
- Get participants new arguments for future discussions

Materials

- Chairs
- Pen and paper to write different positions above chairs

Procedure

Set up a situation involving two sides. At an important point in the role play, have everyone freeze. Ask people to take the opposite role and take up the conversation where it left off. The facilitator may have to help people remember what the last lines of the dialogue were. It can help if the facilitator physically moves people to their new positions and says, "You are now X, and you are now Y". Give people a moment to mentally shift to their new identities and resume the role play. Follow the role play with an evaluation.⁶⁴

⁶⁴ Seeds for change. 2003. 27.

3.3.3 Session – Children 13-16

The Brick Team Exercise

Strengths

The exercise can be used as a warm-up for projects and other planning processes. It can also be used in team building.

Weaknesses

Conversation

Aim

Start a team building process and teach participants how to most effectively communicate for a productive outcome.

Objectives

- Get participants to collaborate during decision-making process
- Can be used as a part of project management preparation exercises
- Get each participant involved into group

Materials

- Place to work for each team
- A number of large index cards (say 10 for each team)
- Small index cards (20 per team)
- Wooden sticks (10 per team) and masking tape in 25 cm (10 inches) strips (10 per team)

Procedure

Participants to build a structure using index cards, masking tape, and wooden sticks.

This structure must be able to support "unaided" a brick (facilitator will provide details). The heights of the structure must be at least 25 centimetres (10 Inches). The brick must be placed at the top of the structure.

This structure must be built at the lowest possible costs and the material can only be bought from the facilitator.

No other material can be used.

You have 20 minutes to build your structure. No "rewards" will be given if a team completes the structure in less time.

No team will be able to test their structure with the brick until all teams have finished. The team building a structure that meets the specifications at the lowest cost wins.

Debrief

Ask the team about what they learned about:

- Team collaboration
- Decision making
- Conflict
- What might they do differently the next time?⁶⁵

⁶⁵ International Association of Facilitators.

Tug O'War

Strengths

Short fun game to break up discussion with some fun physical activity. It's a possible way to regain energy of the group after a break and continue with workshop contents.

Weaknesses

If the group already had energizers and members are energetic, it could possibly get out of hand and violent. Facilitator should be focussed on the group and warn members.

Aim

Demonstrate how creativity is critical to nonviolent problem solving.

Objectives

- Make members think creatively about given task and question the (non) given rules

Materials

- No special preparation
- Time: 5-10 minutes

Procedure

Without discussing the name or objectives of the exercise, ask all the participants to pair up. Have the pairs face each other with both their

of touching feet and that when the facilitator says, 'Go', everyone's goal is to get their partner across that line into your own space.

Watch for any pairs that do something different. The facilitator can stop the pulling at any time by saying, 'Stop', usually just a few seconds will do. Do not let it get so out of hand that someone might get hurt. Ask the group what happened. Generally, the bigger or faster person won. This doesn't take much discussion. If any pairs came up with a solution other than trying to pull each other across, have them describe and demonstrate for the group what they did. If not, take a random participant and get in the starting stance. Now, say to this participant, 'Let's trade places', and with hands still clasped slowly rotate until the facilitator and participant have switched locations.

1. Move on to the next exercise and let the lesson sink in on its own.
2. Make some brief points in lecture fashion:
 - nonviolence is about creative solutions without losers
 - With nonviolent solutions even the bigger 'winner' wins without wasting as much energy, resources, etc.
 - Do not limit yourself by following rules that do not exist
 - If you are less powerful, your only option is to be smarter
3. Open up a discussion on violent vs. nonviolent problem solving.⁶⁶

⁶⁶ Pt'chang Nonviolent Community Safety Group. 2002. 91.

left or right feet forward and touching toe to toe, and the opposite hands clasped as in a hand shake. Tell the group that there is a line between each pair

Two, four, eight exercise

Strengths

Session can bring a group closer together and gets the members to realise that they have basics in common. They also learn how to communicate non-violently with each other during arguing for their own principle.

Weaknesses

Session is time-intensive and needs concentration and motivation from the members. Can be done also more rapidly with less discussion; however it is worth allowing ample time for this exercise.

Aim

Allow deeper discussion on the personal and principled dimensions of nonviolence.

Objectives

- Help develop a higher level of consensus about underpinning principles that are important to that particular group of people
- Task required some debate to reach an agreement
- Members get to reflect on own actions

Materials

- Pens and paper
- Time: 80-90 minutes

Procedure

Begin with a brief outline of consensus. It is based upon trust and respect-it is important to allow 'emergent' ideas and solutions; the aim is not to own your own ideas too strongly to find principles that best reflect where the group is at.

Ask everyone to write his or her own five core 'principles of nonviolence' that seem important to them. (5min)

Ask the group to form pairs. Ask each pair to devise a common five principles that you are both happy with. (10min)

Instruct each pair to find another to form a foursome. Again, between all discuss and decide upon a five core principles that you are happy with. (15min)

Form two equal groups to develop six core principles of nonviolence. Encourage creative merging of ideas. If consensus becomes difficult then allow for greater number of principles to be included. (20min)

Then as a whole group develop a list of 8 core principles of nonviolence. Write these on a wall or chart. If consensus becomes difficult you can again, allow for greater number of principles to be included. (10-20min)

Evaluate and debrief the process. (15min)

Different groups will arrive at different principles. It is sometime worth showing a chart of list of principles as developed by Martin Luther King or others as an example of what other activists have seen as important.⁶⁷

Warm up: Machine

Strengths

Suitable for rather short warming up and earning each other's trust. Also, it is appropriate for getting to know each other and raises the attentiveness of the participants.

Weaknesses

Session is not suitable if the group is already energetic, as it calls for attention and sensitivity.

Aim

The participants get to perceive each other in their movements and behaviour and earn each other's trust.

Objectives

- Notice each other's reaction
- Respond to each other adequately

Materials

- No special preparation
- Time: 5-10 minutes

Procedure

The group members line up in one side of the room. One participant goes into the room, searches for a position and performs one simple movement that repeats itself. To that movement the person makes a suitable sound. Likewise, a second person joins the first one and performs a simple movement and articulates an appropriate sound. The movements and sounds of both participants should intertwine. Little by little all the other group members join, so that everything results into a complex construct of movements and sounds.

Variation: When the machine is finished, the speed of movements and sound can be raised, until a maximum is reached. Afterwards the machine slows down, until it stands still.

Advice: During the game it's helpful to imagine an assembly line, a press, etc. You could build the machine multiple times and pay attention that the single parts of the machine mesh better and better.

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⁶⁷ Pt'chang Nonviolent Community Safety Group. 2002. 78.

⁶⁸ Zap A Lot Improvisationstheater Hamburg. 2003. 14.

3.3.4 Session – Children 16-18

Using Power: Brainstorm/Tableau

Strengths

Group members can recognise how power is permanently used by every one of them and visually see the impact of power using. During the discussion, participants work together and improve each other's ideas and actions. Shy group members don't have to actively play a 'role' in the snapshot but are involved by the expression the role game affected on them.

Weaknesses

It could be that participants don't really have an opinion on a topic. In that case, the facilitator should be provided with some examples of power-using.

Aim

Group members recognise that every action has an impact on the surroundings and power is present in every moment and can be positively used.

Objectives

- Help the group recognise and define approaches to using power that are of particular importance to nonviolent action

Materials

- Flipchart and pen
- Possibly a camera to capture the snapshot

Procedure

Part 1: Definitions and Brainstorms.

The facilitator asks the group what is the first thing that they think of when they hear the word 'power'. Get a few quick responses from the group. The facilitator can then explain that we all use power; what is important is 'how' we use it. Some may use 'Power-Over' – Power used to gain or maintain domination or control over others. Write that term on the board/paper and ask group to brainstorm examples. Allow for discussion. Then ask group what an alternative way of using power may be? Some may have heard of 'Power-With' – power used collectively or co-operatively as a group of equals. Write that term up as well and allow for group to brainstorm examples of power-with being applied.

Part 2: Power Tableaus, Small groups of 3-4.

Choose one of these scenarios of power-over that was listed and as a group create a 'snapshot' (a freeze-frame that represents that somehow). Ask the participants to notice how they feel in their 'role'. One group at a time come out of your snap shot and look around the room for a moment - notice expressions, body language, etc. Repeat this for Power-with and Power from as time allows. Then discuss and clarify the consequences of using Power.

Always check carefully if everybody in the group has understood the two terms and the

- Time: 15-30 minutes

difference between them. Allow time for questions, comments, and discussion.⁶⁹

⁶⁹ Pt'chang Nonviolent Community Safety Group. 2002. 89.

Get to Know Each Other: Everyone is a Liar (Two Truths and one Lie)

Strengths

Useful and fun for starting a meeting or after a break in a group where participants don't know each other or don't know much about each other.

Weaknesses

Individuals who don't like the idea of "lying" may have a difficult time with this.

Aim

To help everyone to learn names and personal/professional information.

Objectives

- Icebreaking through the possibility of making up stories

Materials

- Possibly flipchart and pen
- Time: 10-15 minutes

Procedure

Facilitator writes three statements on the board. Two statements are true, and one is a lie. Example:

I have been teaching for 10 years.
I have a pet cat called, "Mini"
I lived in Rome for a year.

Invite participants to ask "lie detector" questions to get information in order to determine which statement is false. For example:

Teaching - Where have you taught? What have you taught? What year did you start?

Pet - How old is Mini? What does Mini eat? Where do you keep Mini?

Rome - Where did you live in Rome? What language was spoken in Rome?

Participants vote on which statement is a lie. Reveal which are truths and which are lies.

Place participants in small groups (3 or 4 works well). Small groups repeat steps 1 - 3, individuals write down their truths and lie on paper first, then share one by one while others ask questions, vote on which statement is a lie.

Have participants introduce each other to the large group.⁷⁰

⁷⁰ International Association of Facilitators

Imagine the Future: Setting Goals

Strengths

If you have a fixed group which identifies with the same ideals and wishes to change something in their surrounding or start a campaign, the session is perfectly designed to specify the action and the proceeding. Further it can be used to encourage every single participant to think about their own future goals and implement the exercise by pairing the participants and discuss in these groups the goals and proceedings of each individual.

Weaknesses

The goal which is set could seem too high for the participants.

Aim

Develop goals, including short and medium range goals and at the same time recognise potential dangers and how to avoid them.

Objectives

- Give an idea of what the short and medium range goals for a campaign might be
- Develop steps to get there

Materials

- No special preparation
- Time: 5-10 minutes

Procedure

To 'imagine the future' start by placing a vision the group shares at the top of a piece flip chart paper. Underneath write goals that the group thinks would need to be achieved to make that vision a reality. Ask the group to choose one of the goals that is most appropriate for them to work toward, and to assign a date in the future when it could be reached. Encourage the group to imagine they are already in that year; their vision has been fulfilled! Ask the question: what conditions had to be met for the goal to become a reality? What changes needed to take place? How did people's attitudes and behaviour change? Were there changes in government policy, or in other institutions? When did these changes happen?

Place the important changes on the paper, beginning with the goal and working backwards from the goal (future) to where you are now (the present). Once you have a complete picture, all the way from the campaign goal to the present moment, it might be helpful to prioritise the changes you need to achieve.

You could use a table from the number 4 (sufficient), to 0 (irrelevant/neutral). Changes which are irrelevant should be taken off the chart. In addition, you might add changes which would be threatening to the vision or campaign goal, and which need to be avoided. This can help to make you aware of dangers to your strategy. Encourage reflection on each change, moving further from the goal back to the present situation.⁷¹

⁷¹ Graswurzelrevolution - for a nonviolent libertarian society. 2014. 197.

From Activity to Discussion

Strengths

Well-fitting as preparation for further discussion about conflict.

Weaknesses

Session suitable for calm, attentive atmosphere. Unfitting for energetic group dynamic.

Aim

Session suitable for calm, attentive atmosphere. Unfitting for energetic group dynamic.

Objectives

- Makes participants aware of everyday communication and appropriate ways to communicate positively
- During the task participants need to find a consensus and discuss respectfully

Materials

- note taking material for participants
- Time: 20-30 minutes, depending on group number

Procedure

The task: Write down five points which characterise a good conflict. If participants do not have personal experience of a good conflict, then think hypothetically.

Ask the participants to re-write the exact opposite of the first five points.

Share the participants into small groups and ask them to choose which three points they think represent the greatest problems in conflicts according to their lists.

The group can then brainstorm around how to transform a destructive conflict management to constructive conflict management around the points they have chosen.

Present the findings in the whole group.

Spectrum and Cross Spectrum (Also known as Barometer)

Strengths

Group members can evaluate how different opinions emerge and get an understanding of each other. At the same time participants decide together what makes an action violent or nonviolent.

Weaknesses

Positions of participants can have a great difference, which need space for evaluation.

Aim

Test or illustrate the breadth of opinion within a group and identify what makes an effective action.

Objectives

- Test or develop specific proposal for effective nonviolent action that the group can agree on
- Identify what nonviolence is and why it should be used
- Explore reasons or experiences for opinions of group members

Materials

- Rope, Ribbon or masking tape, large enough to make a grid that the group can stand on
- Paper and pen
- Time: 45 minutes

Procedure

Identify a space where group members can place themselves along a line. The two ends of the line represent polar opposites: agreement, disagreement, 'I would/I wouldn't'. Present a clear statement or scenario and ask people to stand in a place on the spectrum that represents how they feel about it.

Make it clear that there are no 'right' or 'wrong' answers, just different opinions, and that it is important to listen to each other and try to understand each other's' perspectives. Encourage to say 'I think that...' or 'I feel that...'. Everyone should speak for themselves. Ask participants to explain why they have stood where they are; encourage brief, snappy responses. If the group is large, invite participants to discuss with those near them why they have chosen to stand where they have; this helps everyone to participate and voice their position, even if there isn't time to hear everyone in the full group.

Variation: 'Cross spectrum': effectively, two spectrums on different axes. Possible: labelling ends 'violent/nonviolent' and 'effective/ineffective'. Going through a range of action scenarios; participants have to decide to what degree they think an action is violent/nonviolent etc. As above ask participants to say why they stood where they did. Use examples that might be controversial.

Participants might be tempted to immediately move into a discussion after the first person has explained why they have stood where they are. Watch for this – if it happens, ask participants to

complete the sentence "I am standing here because ...".⁷²

⁷² Graswurzelrevolution - for a nonviolent libertarian society. 2014. 215.

3.4 Micro- and Meso-Level Stakeholders (Adults)

The focus groups are aimed at two different sets of stakeholders. The first set consists of the parents of the children and the second group consists of a mixed-group of school and extracurricular education professionals and other country-specific stakeholders with expertise relating to refugee children and children with a migratory background.

3.4.1 Session – Focus Group: Parents

The Focus Group method (see description 3.1.1) is the more adapted method to collect the different opinions of the parents group.

Build the parents group:

The ideal number of participants in each group is between a minimum of six and a maximum of twelve. Six is the minimum required for group dynamics function properly. Twelve is the maximum if we want to avoid the emergence of subgroups; the ideal number is ten participants.

Duration:

It takes a minimum of one hour and a maximum of three hours. Regarding the duration of the focus group itself (to be multiplied by the number of groups), it is advisable to include the time required for:

- Preparation of the interview schedule;
- The entire transcription of the Focus Group recordings;
- The synthesis and analysis of the results.

Preparation:

- Prepare the group agreement
- Take a recorder
- Develop the grid. The grid provides the framework for parent's group discussions. It is a guide and a tool for animation. It can be presented either in a schematic form or in the form of a questionnaire. It must:
 - Follow the logical progression of the analysis plan which defines the thematic groups.
 - Consist of open questions.
 - Clear questions, simple language, accessible to all.
 - Non-biased, non-connotative questions to guide the debate.
 - Short questions.
 - Questions addressing only one idea.
 - A first question that is inclusive, encouraging and facilitative.

Execution:

First an introduction and presentation of the project has been made. Develop a group agreement with the parents group or develop one with the group. Make sure that all the parents feel equal and safe.

Summarize and explain the purpose of the group and what is expected of the participants.

It is important to emphasize and, insisting upon the anonymity of the debates, to explain the technical necessity of the recording of the debates, so that there is no ambiguity in the minds of the participants.

Helped from your grid, you can initiate the discussion. If the facilitator notices some difficulties for the participants to talk about issues because of the presence of the both genders. The group can be split per gender to build a safe space.

The role of the facilitator in the focus group

The facilitator must:

- Direct the dynamics of the group, respecting the grid and maintaining the debates within the identified themes.
- Avoid the so-called “contamination of the group”
- Act as a moderator in the discussions.
- Always remain neutral, never give his point of view on an issue.

The facilitator should ask sub-questions to get participants to share their experience and to reveal themselves in their personal experiences.

He avoids any non-verbal expression and responds to all questions that the group asks about the content. He leads the group without guiding the content but does provide guidance in relation to the procedure. Not authoritative and rigid but flexible, He looks at the person speaking to show him that he is important.

3.4.2 Session – Focus Group: Meso-Level Experts

Depending on the size of the group, it is advisable to choose one of the following two methods:

- For less than 8 participants – Focus group (see description 3.1.1)
- For more than 8 participants – World Café.

The World Café Method

Concept:

This method was developed in the 1990s by two management consultants: Juanita Brown and David Isaacs.⁷³ They build the concept on the assumption that people are knowledgeable, that

⁷³ <http://actioncatalogue.eu/method/7402>

they are creative and that they can resolve the problem they are facing together (collective wisdom concept)⁷⁴. The world café method provides the opportunity for the people concerned to reflect in a collective manner.

This method can be modified and adapted to your context (number of tables, facilitator or not, way to conclude the world café session).

The different steps of a World Café session:⁷⁵

- Prepare one topic-question for each table. Each table will have one subject to be discussed. In our case: Intercultural competences, psychosocial wellbeing and gender issues.
- Set the tables with the required material.
- Place a facilitator at each table.
- When all the people are sitting at the different tables, present the World Café Etiquette. We should have between 3 and 6 people at each table.
- After the first round, the facilitator summarises what has already been discussed so that the next group can continue.
- The group will be divided into 3 small groups. Every group spends 30 minutes at each table to discuss the subject.
- At the end, when all the groups have been to all the tables, the one who is responsible for the table will make a concluding speech about the reflections of the different groups on the subject. Individuals are invited to share insights or other results from their conversations with the rest of the large group. These results are reflected visually in a variety of ways, such as a graphic recording.
- In the context of our research project, you can invite some participants to an expert interview at the end of the session.

Material:

On each table you need: Paper, pens, a timer and a recorder.

The World Café Etiquette:

- Presentation
- Goal (Developing policies for migrant children in different levels in the EU, for example)
- Procedure: Every table will have a topic linked to a question/problem

⁷⁴ <http://www.theworldcafe.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/07/Cafe-To-Go-Revised.pdf>

⁷⁵ This is one of the possible approximations within a methodology that is flexible. Please check: (<http://www.theworldcafe.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/07/Cafe-To-Go-Revised.pdf>), since the methodology is relatively flexible and adaptable, but this would be the original approach and design

- Expected behaviour attended (Group agreement)

The role of the facilitator:

If you have enough staff, put one facilitator on each table, otherwise designate someone in each group every time.

The role of the facilitator on each table is to maintain the participants' focus on the subject. He/she has to moderate and take notes.

The facilitator is responsible for encouraging people to connect ideas from previous conversations with other tables. His/her responsibility is to maintain a high level of energy and the fluidity of conversations. They must be selected according to their ability to listen, to get along with others, to stay objective and to stay focused.

3.5 Macro-Level Stakeholders – Expert Interviews

For interviewing the expert, there are three main methods in the research field:

- **Structured or formal interviews** involves the researcher working through a questionnaire or interview schedule as part of a social survey.
- **Unstructured or Informal interviews** (also called discovery interviews) are more like a guided conversation. The interviewer has a definite idea about the questions to be asked, but it doesn't follow a schedule.
- **Semi-Structured interviews** are those in which the researcher has a list of questions, but "they are free to ask further, differentiated questions based on the responses give."⁷⁶

For the purpose of the qualitative research regarding the three core indicators it is advisable to prepare a guided interview. A guide interview is intended to ensure "that the same general areas of information are collected from each interviewee; this provides more focus than the conversational approach, but still allows a degree of freedom and adaptability in getting the information from the interviewee."⁷⁷

Development of a Guided Interview⁷⁸

⁷⁶ Thompson. 2016.

⁷⁷ Valenzuela. 4.

⁷⁸ In accordance with Cornelia Helfferich 2005: Die Qualität qualitativer Daten. Manuel für die Durchführung qualitativer Interviews. Lehrbuch, Wiesbaden.

First, you have to know what you will be talking about. Gather all the information about the person you want to interview (publications, work position, interviews and so on) to be able to build a specific interview guide. For a guided interview, the most important question you have to deal with is: "What do we want to know?" Once you have defined this, you can brainstorm in order to develop questions which might help you to gather all the information you need.

If you have a large pool of questions the questions must be checked for appropriateness and any unsuitable questions must be deleted. The remaining questions must be sorted in terms of content and/or topics, in terms of open narrative requests, and specific demands. The interview should have a funnel form. At the beginning, the questions have to be open and at the end, more specific. Try to build a narrative logic into the progress of the interview.

Structuring the questions:

When you have got your guide, you should structure your questions. Cornelia Helfferich proposes a system in which the questions are divided into 3 groups:

1. Key question: It serves as a narrative request/stimulus and is formulated very openly: "Please tell me how you grew up?"
2. Maintenance question: It does not provide a new topic, but maintains the narrative flow, or gives impulses for associative thoughts: "What went on?", "What else are you thinking of?" "And what else?", "And next?" "What else do you associate with "X"?"
3. Concrete inquiries: Here, questions can be formulated on content-related aspects that have not yet arisen in the conversation.

Tips

- No suggestive questions,
- No judgment, assessment or comments, even empathic comments, and
- No double questions.
- Adapt your language to the person you are talking with: adapt your sociolinguistic level.
- If you don't understand the answer, ask for reformulation. Don't make any suppositions about what you think that you understood.

Bibliography

Advocacy and communication. "Common facilitation challenges". March 2019. http://www.advocacyandcommunication.org/wp-content/themes/acs/docs/resources/redesigned_tools/ACS_Common_Facilitative_Challenges1.pdf

Cranley LA, Cummings GG, Profetto-McGrath J, Toth F, Estabrooks CA. "Facilitation roles and characteristics associated with research use by healthcare professionals": a scoping review. *BMJ Open*. 2017;7(8): e014384. Published 2017 Aug 11. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2016-014384.

Easwaramoorthy M., Zarinpoush Fataneh. "Interviewing for researchers". 2006. March 2019. http://sectorsource.ca/sites/default/files/resources/files/tipsheet6_interviewing_for_research_en_0.pdf.

Gorski, Paul. "Guide for Setting Ground Rules". 1995-2018. March 2019. <http://www.edchange.org/multicultural/activities/groundrules.html>.

Graswurzelrevolution - for a nonviolent libertarian society. Handbook for Nonviolent Campaigns. War Resisters' International. 2014.

Halls Jonathan. "A powerful way to minimize disruptive behaviours". 2017. March 2019. <https://www.td.org/insights/a-powerful-way-to-minimize-disruptive-behaviors>.

Ing. Heidenberger, Burkhard. „Vortrag, Seminar, Kurs, Workshop, Webinar, Kongress, Barcamp – worin bestehen die Unterschiede?“. March 2019. <https://www.zeitbluten.com/news/vortrag-seminar-kurs-workshop-webinar-kongress-barcamp/>.

Helfferich, Cornelia. „Die Qualität qualitativer Daten. Manuel für die Durchführung qualitativer Interviews.“ Wiesbaden. 2005.

Hinkey, L. and Engleby, Laura. "Facilitation Training". 2003. March 2019. [/navigating-in-rough-seas-public-issues-and-conflict-management-training-manual-\(2003\).pdf](/navigating-in-rough-seas-public-issues-and-conflict-management-training-manual-(2003).pdf).

International Association of Facilitators. Warm Up Games and Exercises. N.a. March 2019. <https://www.sessionlab.com/methods/everyone-is-a-liar-two-truths-and-one-lie>.

Kepner-Tregoe. "The Value of a Facilitator in Organizational Problem Solving and Decision Making". 2011. March 2019. <http://kepner-tregoe.de/knowledge-center/articles/the-value-of-a-facilitator-in-organizational-problem-solving-and-decision-making/>.

Larock Otim, Rita. "Facilitation Skills Training Manual: A Facilitator's Handbook". 2013. March 2019.

Laurel and Associates. "How to Handle Difficult Participants?". 2010. March 2019. <https://www.hse.ie/eng/about/who/qid/other-quality-improvement-programmes/opensdisclosure/opensdiscfiles/guidetomanagingdifficultparticipants.pdf>.

Mann, Tony. "Facilitation in management". 2013. March 2019. <https://www.trainingjournal.com/articles/feature/facilitation-management>.

Pt'chang Nonviolent Community Safety Group. Trainers' Resource Manual. 2005. March 2019. <https://www.thechangeagency.org/pdfs/nonviolence-trainers-resource-manual/>.

Seed for change. "Facilitation tools for meetings and workshops. A compilation of tools and techniques for working in groups and facilitating meetings or workshops". 2009. March 2019. <https://seedsforchange.org.uk/tools.pdf> /.

PRO-IDEAL Plus. "D.3.2 – Concept and methodology of Interactive Workshops". 2010. March 2019. <https://cordis.europa.eu/docs/projects/cnect/4/246644/080/deliverables/001-D32Conceptandmethodologyofinteractiveworkshops.pdf>.

Seed for change. "Group agreements for workshops and meetings". 2009. March 2019. <https://www.seedsforchange.org.uk/groupagree>.

Seeds for Change. "Strengthening co-operation, Empowering resistance". N.a. March 2019. <https://www.seedsforchange.org.uk/consensus.pdf>.

The World Café Community Foundation. "A quick reference guide for hosting World Café". 2015. <http://www.theworldcafe.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/07/Cafe-To-Go-Revised.pdf>

Pénissard, Didier. "Comment gérer les personnalités dominantes?". 2018. March 2019. <https://developpement-personnel-club.com/comment-gerer-les-personnalites-dominantes/>.

Rotary International. "Effective Facilitation Guide". March 2019. http://clubrunner.blob.core.windows.net/00000050005/en-ca/files/sitepage/rli-curriculum/effective-facilitation-download-%28pdf%29/effective_facilitation.pdf.

Slocum Nikki. "Méthodes participatives: un guide pour l'utilisateur, Le world café". 2006. <http://bel.uqtr.ca/id/eprint/187>

Spiral – Université de Liège. Le Focus Group. 2011-2019. March 2019. <http://www.spiral.ulg.ac.be/fr/outils/focus-group/>.

Thayer-Hart, Nancy. "Facilitator tool Guide for helping groups get results". University of Wisconsin-madison. 2007. March 2019. <http://miroslawdabrowski.com/downloads/Facilitation/Facilitator%20Tool%20Kit.pdf>.

Thompson. „Interviews in social research: advantages and disadvantages". 2016. March 2019. <https://revisesociology.com/2016/01/23/interviews-in-social-research-advantages-and-disadvantages/>.

UNHCR. Action for the rights of children. "Outil pédagogique pour les formateurs". March 2019. <https://www.unhcr.org/fr/4b309d681d.pdf>

UNHCR. Action for the rights of children. "Tools, situation analysis". 1999. March 2019. <https://www.unhcr.org/3f82da124.pdf>.

UNHCR. Skeels Anna. "Listen and learn, Participatory assessment with children and adolescents". United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees. 2012. March 2019. <https://www.refworld.org/pdfid/4fffe4af2.pdf>.

UNHCR. "Participatory assessment in operations". N.a. March 2019. <https://www.unhcr.org/450e920e2.pdf>.

UNHCR. "Participatory Assessment with Children and Adolescents". 2012. March 2019. <https://www.refworld.org/pdfid/4fffe4af2.pdf>.

University of Virginia. "The role of the facilitator". March 2019. <http://www.virginia.edu/processsimplification/resources/Facilitator.pdf>.

WHO. "Gender, Equity and Human rights". March 2019. <https://www.who.int/gender-equity-rights/understanding/participation-definition/en/>.

Valenzuela, Dapzury, Shrivastava, Pallavi. "Interview as a qualitative method for qualitative research." <https://www.public.asu.edu/~kroel/www500/Interview%20Fri.pdf>.

Zamora, Durán Grace, Diamond, Tina. "Training Module, Facilitator's guide". 2012. March 2019. <https://rti4success.org/sites/default/files/Training%20Module%20Facilitator%27s%20Guide.pdf>

Zap A Lot Improvisationstheater Hamburg. "Spiele & Übungen für das Improvisationstheater". 2003. March 2019. http://www.impro-theater.de/dmdocuments/spielesammlung_zapalot.pdf .